

Relation between Organizational Climate and Personnel Performance Assessment in a Tourist Service Company

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Abstract—This investigation aims at analyzing and determining the relation between two very important variables in the human resource management: The organizational climate and the performance assessment. This study aims at contributing with knowledge in the search of the relation between the mentioned variables because the literature still does not provide solid evidence to this respect and the cases revised are incipient to reach conclusions enabling a typology about this relation. To this regard, a correlational and cross-sectional perspective was adopted in which quantitative and qualitative techniques were chosen with the total of the workers of the tourist service company PTS Peru. In order to measure the organizational climate, the OCQ (Organization Climate Questionnaire) from was used; it has 50 items and measures 9 dimensions of the Organizational Climate. Also, to assess performance, a questionnaire with 21 items and 6 dimensions was designed. As a means of assessment, a focus group was prepared and was applied to a worker in every area of the company. Additionally, interviews to human resources experts were conducted. The results of the investigation show a clear relation between the organizational climate and the personnel performance assessment as well as a relation between the nine dimensions of the organizational climate and the work performance in general and with some of its dimensions.

Keywords—Job performance, human resource management, organization climate, performance assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE current business context shows more complex scenarios every time transforming the human resources area or people management into a strategic ally and essential pillar to achieve the formulated organizational objectives [1]. Many organizations aim at intensifying their efforts by executing different programs related to human management in order to offer their collaborators better working conditions or scenarios and develop a better life quality. Hence, it is of paramount importance to understand the organizational climate, that is, to know how the workers perceive the different organizational elements; and, in this way, work on those elements and obtain more satisfaction, output and quality in what they perform [2], as well as assess the performance of their collaborators to know the way they

develop their job [3], and be able to determine and design plans, such as promotions and career path [4].

It is vital for the companies, particularly the ones providing services, to know the expectations and perceptions of the collaborators about the internal environment that the company offers, to the extent that this has an impact on the service practices to internal and external clients. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the variables related to aspects such as satisfaction, engagement, motivation or performance which becomes increasingly more important.

Based on the above, the need to conduct studies, diagnosis and investigations about organizational climate and job performance is determined in order to identify the possible relation between both variables and thus achieve a better understanding. This process takes place to the extent in which literature does not show a solid reference since the authors are a little reserved and cautious in expressing their ideas about the relation between organizational climate and job performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Organizational Climate

It is said that Lewin introduced this concept in the thirties while conducting studies about leadership where he regarded it as a bonding element, that is, a connector between the person and the environment or place where they perform their labor [5]. He also indicated that the workers' performance was related to their environment, that is, the climate and personality [6]. However, it is at the end of the sixties that this concept becomes a popular topic, to the extent that, it arises in a moment in which it is necessary to pay attention to global phenomena having direct involvement with the organization [7].

There are many conceptual references dealing with organizational climate [8]-[15], such references mention relevant aspects to be considered, such as values, motivation, influence in the behaviour and performance, among others.

There are two perspectives when talking about climate approaches, an objective and subjective perspective, referring to the organizational factor as an objective element and to the individual factors as a subjective element [16]. From the objective approach, it is mentioned that the climate is owed particularly to organizational factors which constitute the internal environment of the individual in the organization, for example the culture, the behavior, the environment, the

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organizational structure, among others. On the other hand, the subjective approach states that the climate is an individual attribute by claiming that the climate basis is the individual perception of the organizational situation where they perform. An additional approach is the result of the interaction or union of the objective and subjective perspective, in other words, the interaction of the organizational factors with the individual ones. This approach corresponds to the perception of organizational factors derived from the interaction of the individuals [6]. Within this context, it is important to refer to the factors acting in the organizational climate, that is, elements which integrate and generate an impact upon the climate. Aspects such as leadership and the type of managers' supervision on their subordinated, the formal system and the organization structure such as communication, promotions, incentives, payments, etc., are factors acting in the organizational climate [17]. The acting factors vary from organization to organization, since every organization has unique characteristics, elements to be considered among the climate factors are: Attitude, the perception of the employees with their environment or the place where they work; engagement, commitment and dedication to their work and organization [18]; motivation, the effort to contribute in the achievement of the goals and objectives established by the organization [19].

Along the time, as mentioned, the organization climate has become a relevant topic to the extent that it allows to know the factors affecting the organization internally and externally and to timely identify problems affecting the performance of its members. Organizational climate is important to the extent in which it allows to obtain information about the feeling of the collaborators about the elements constituting the organization, such as work methodology, organization structure, and supervision degree from the superiors, among others. Likewise, it allows knowing the existing working conditions, the communication mechanisms and the current work relation [20].

Researchers have focused their attention on defining the climate and in separating it in dimensions in order to know and understand it to concretize it better [21], and because, the dimensions of the organizational climate have an impact on the behavior of the collaborators [22]. Litwin and Stringer determined nine dimensions which are part of the climate in a company. These dimensions are related to the characteristics of an organization and are perceived by their members [13]. Based on these dimensions that Litwin and Stringer in 1968, created one of the most used tools to measure the organizational climate: the OCQ (Organizational Climate Questionnaire), which measures nine dimensions: organizational structure, responsibility, rewards, challenge, relationships, cooperation, performance standards, conflicts and identity; and it is a valuable and reliable questionnaire [16]. The dimensions and meaning of each one are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
 ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE DIMENSIONS [13]

Dimension	Concept
Structure	Appreciation of rules, policies and procedures to be fulfilled to perform the tasks.
Responsibility	Autonomy level in the decision making regarding the fulfilled tasks a worker can take.
Reward	Perception about the existence of equity in rewards and promotions system.
Challenge	Perception of the difficulty of the assigned tasks.
Relationships	Interpersonal relationships between coworkers and at a senior staff level.
Cooperation	Sense of cooperation perceived in the company among peers and in the higher and inferior levels.
Performance Standards	Perception of the company interest in the regulation fulfillment, procedures, policies and performance guidelines.
Conflicts	Worker's perception of the ways and mechanisms implemented for conflict resolution in the organization and the way to confront them.
Identity	Sense of belonging to the organization and to the work team.

B. Performance Assessment

Currently, the performance assessment is the most used way to estimate or measure the individual performance at work and their development potential. Companies attach great importance in measuring the collaborators' performance to design diverse action plans. Several authors explain the performance assessment [4], [23]-[28], highlighting aspects such as assessing knowledge, skills and attitudes, the importance of the relation between clear policies and procedures with the expected result of the collaborators, decision making on promotions, training, development; among others.

Assessing people's performance is important, to the extent it enables to distinguish workers who perform a good job from the ones who only fulfill it or, in some cases, fake. Also, it helps to identify the workers who only obey their supervisors and the ones who do more than it is required. Lastly, it helps to stimulate the objective supervision and serves as a motivation for the collaborator to perfect their task [3].

A group of authors presents several reasons why the assessment is important in organizations. Some of those authors' appreciations are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
 IMPORTANCE OF THE PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

Author	Performance Assessment Importance
[26]	The assessment provides a valuation on which to base possible salary increases, promotions, relocations and, often, dismissal. Additionally, it enables to communicate the employees how their job performance is going on, indicating what to be changed in their behavior, attitudes, skills or knowledge.
[29]	The importance of the assessment lies in the definition of specific criteria for the job position according to the performance to be measured. The rewards granted to the individuals or groups are justified and the development experiences that the assessed needs to improve their performance in the current position are defined.
[28]	The performance assessment is important because it helps determine the training needs in the personnel, development needs, succession plans, and career path. It provides feedback to the employees about the way they perform their duties and it helps in the decision of promotions, relocations and dismissals.
[4]	The assessment is important to make decisions on promotions and increases; it also allows to develop a plan to correct any deficiency found. Lastly, it helps in the professional planning by providing the chance to review the employee career plans.

It is necessary for the objectives of the assessment to be connected to the ones of the organizations. The first objective is the performance improvement, which derives from the translation of the subordinates' assessment results. As a second objective, the compensation adjustments are mentioned since the assessments help the responsible of an area to determine the employees who deserve salary increases and additional benefits. As a third objective, it is mentioned that the decisions of relocations and promotions are to be based on the assessment results. The last objective indicates the need to establish training and development plans, since a bad performance may indicate a need for training not fulfilled and a good performance the need to make the most of the potential to develop it for future positions [30].

When the performance assessment is properly focused, planned and executed, it provides short, middle and long term benefits for the organization as well as the collaborators. The benefits can be diverse and the main beneficiaries of a performance assessment process are the workers, the manager and the organization [31].

In the case of the manager, the assessment allows to determine the development and acting of the subordinates in their work, based on the criteria and factors of assessment previously established for the assessment. Therefore, the planning phase is vital for the assessment. Regarding the subordinates, it allows them to know the game rules, that is, the aspects of behavior and performance most valued by the company. Lastly, for the organization, it allows to assess the potential of the collaborator in a short, middle, and long term and to define the contribution of each employee.

C. Relation between Organizational Climate and Job Performance

When trying to explain the relation between the climate and performance, it is important to study Silva's words [16], who mentions that to understand this relation, it is necessary to consider the effects of the climate on the behaviors and attitudes of the collaborators as well as on the organizational performance. That is, it is required to consider the impact of the climate on an individual and organizational level in as far as the perceptions and ideas that the collaborators develop about their work environment play an important role on: how are the tasks and functions defined, what is the reward systems based on, how are decisions controlled, how is the kind of current communication in the organization defined, among other aspects.

Authors are reserved and cautious when trying to express their ideas about the existing relation between climate and performance [16]. They indicate that the climate is a tool which can help us understand and improve the performance of the individual as well as the organization, and explain the potential impact that the climate has on the performance: They do not claim the existence of a clear relation, but they consider the climate as a predictor element of performance.

According to empirical evidence, the relation between climate and performance are not as easy to understand and are not as convincing as the relation between climate and job

satisfaction. [32]. On the other side, climates considered as the most innovative manage to have a positive impact on the performance of the individuals and the organization, while the climates which are not so structured or static cause a negative effect on the performance [33]. Some research has revealed that the dimensions of climate that have been most related to the performance of people are supervision, support, risk, decision making, rewards, peer relationships and structure. [33].

III. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is to demonstrate the hypothesis that indicates the existence of a direct relation between the organizational climate and work performance as well as the nine dimensions of the organizational climate with the general work performance and between dimensions of the organizational climate with the dimensions of the work performance in the personnel of the company PTS Peru of the city of Lima for 2015.

The methodology used for this investigation is a mixed approach, since it is composed of a quantitative and qualitative part, with a non-experimental descriptive investigation design to the extent that an already existing situation is studied and upon which there is no control about the study variables neither can there be an influence on the relation between such variables [34]. Additionally, it is, cross-sectional-correlational: Cross-sectional because information about the variables is sought after in a set amount of time; and correlational, in the way that the relation between the study variables and their specific dimensions [34]. It is important to consider that the study population corresponds to the workers of the Tourist Service Company PTS Peru, 21 workers.

A. Case Study as an Investigation Methodology

In order to understand the complex organizational phenomena, exploratory and comprehensive investigations are necessary [35]. Therefore, an investigation design associated to case studies is an appropriate method to be able to understand the reality of the organization and so reach conclusions applicable to such reality. In order to understand the behavior of companies and organizations, diverse methods coming from the contact with the study object are necessary, consequently new explanations for these phenomena can be generated [36]. Therefore, the case study is a useful methodology in the business area. The study case in the business areas is becoming more accepted, particularly due to the fact that the information obtained is used in the decision making of the company [35].

There are three important reasons why the case study is a viable methodology for companies. First, an object is studied in its natural status, which leads to understand the reality and generates theories about what is observed. Second, it allows knowing the nature and complexity of the processes existing in the organization. Lastly, a case study allows deepening in a topic on which little or no study has been done previously [37].

B. Procedures to Gather Information and Analysis Plan

Once the permit was obtained, measuring instruments were applied to the workers. Then, a guideline was developed to carry out a confirmatory focus group. To this end, a worker was quoted from each area of the company, having previously explained the procedures to be followed according to the results of the investigation. Finally, interviews were conducted with experts drawn from the matrix of gathering information.

Regarding the measuring tools, two questionnaires were used: one for organizational climate and other to measure labor performance. With respect to the organizational climate, the OCQ [Organizational Climate Questionnaire] was applied; this tool has 50 items and measures 9 dimensions: organizational structure, rewards, responsibility, warmth, support, conflict, organizational identity, performance standards and risk in the decision making was applied. This tool is answered according to a Likert Scale with four options (from 1 strongly agree to 4 strongly disagree). To measure performance, a questionnaire was designed; this has 21 items and measures 6 dimensions: Goal orientation, quality, interpersonal relationships, initiative, teamwork and organization. This tool is answered by a Likert scale with five options (from 1 very low to 5 very high).

With respect to the analysis plan, it is necessary to indicate that first, the statistic validations corresponding to the measuring tools were executed by means of the Cronbach's alpha. In the case of the Organizational Climate, the result was $\alpha=0.894$, while in the performance assessment, the result of the statistic validation was $\alpha=0.861$. That is, both measurement scales have a very high reliability.

For the quantitative analysis of the results obtained from the measurement instruments, the correlation based on the Spearman's coefficient was used, in order to know the relation between the study variables and their specific dimensions. Also, this tool was used basically because of the non-normal distribution of the variables and the quantity of the sample. In these cases, this type of correlation must be prioritized [38].

IV. RESULTS

Through the correlational analysis, it was found that the organizational climate is related to the job performance by presenting a significance of 0.022 ($p<0.05$) and a correlation coefficient of 0.657. Table III shows the correlational analysis obtained from both variables. Also, the correlational analysis showed a relation among all the dimensions of the organizational climate with the general job performance. The following dimensions showed the strongest and most significant relations: Warmth with a significance of 0.003 ($p<0.05$); organizational structure, with a significance of 0.007 ($p<0.05$); and support with 0.0075 ($p<0.05$). On the other hand, the dimensions with the weakest relations were: Conflict with a significance of 0.028 ($p<0.05$); responsibility with a significance of 0.042 ($p<0.05$); and risk, with a significance of 0.0439 ($p<0.05$). Table IV shows the correlational analysis obtained from the organizational climate dimensions with the general job performance.

TABLE III
CORRELATION GENERAL ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE AND GENERAL JOB PERFORMANCE

		General Job Performance
General	Correlation Coefficient	.657**
Organizational Climate	Sig. (bilateral)	0.022
	N	20

TABLE IV
CORRELATIONS BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE DIMENSIONS AND GENERAL JOB PERFORMANCE

		General Job Performance
Correlation Coefficient	Reward	0.524*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.0092
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Responsibility	0.475
Sig. (bilateral)		0.042
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Organizational Structure	0.629**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.007
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Decision Making Risk	0.484
Sig. (bilateral)		0.0439
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Warmth	0.652**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.003
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Performance norms	0.562*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.0124
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Support	0.613**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.0075
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Conflict	0.501
Sig. (bilateral)		0.028
	N	20
Correlation Coefficient	Identity	0.536*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.017
	N	20

Regarding the correlational analysis between the particular dimensions of the climate and the performance, it was found that the structure dimension (climate) has a relation with the goal orientation dimension (performance) by presenting a significance of 0.03 ($p<0.05$). Likewise, the dimension responsibility (climate) has a relation with the goal orientation dimension (performance) by presenting a significance of 0.029 ($p<0.05$). The reward dimension (climate) has a relation with the quality and initiative dimensions (performance) by presenting a significance of 0.025 ($p<0.05$) y 0.0174 ($p<0.05$) respectively. In the risk dimension (climate) there is a link with the organization dimension (performance) by presenting a significance of 0.031 ($p<0.05$); warmth (climate) is related to the interpersonal relationship dimensions and teamwork (performance) at obtaining degree of significance of 0.016 ($p<0.05$) and 0.0423 ($p<0.05$), respectively. It is also relevant to consider that support (climate) has a relation with the quality and teamwork dimensions (performance) with significance of 0.043 ($p<0.05$) and 0.012 ($p<0.05$), respectively; standards (climate) is related to the quality and

organization dimensions (performance) with a significance of 0.016 ($p < 0.05$) and 0.004 ($p < 0.05$), correspondingly; lastly, the identity dimension (climate) is related to the initiative and goal orientation dimensions (performance) with significance of 0.017 ($p < 0.05$) and 0.042 ($p < 0.05$), respectively.

It is important to highlight that responsibility dimension (climate) with goal orientation dimension (performance), reward (climate) with quality (performance), support (climate) with teamwork (performance), standards (climate) with quality (performance), standards (climate) with organization (performance), are the dimensions that presented the highest coefficients of correlation and the strongest relations, on the other hand, conflict dimension (climate) has no relation with any dimension of the job performance (see Table VII). Also, within the correlational analysis, relevant information about the organizational climate was found. Regarding this aspect, the dimensions which have a relation with the organizational climate in the Company PTS Peru are: Structure with a significance of 0.011 ($p < 0.05$); responsibility with 0.009 ($p < 0.05$); warmth with 0.006 ($p < 0.05$); conflict with 0.001 ($p < 0.05$); reward with 0 ($p < 0.05$); identity with 0 ($p < 0.05$); and, lastly, support with a significance of 0 ($p < 0.05$). The risk and standards dimensions did not present relation with the general organizational climate.

TABLE V
 CORRELATION BETWEEN THE ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE DIMENSIONS AND THE GENERAL ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE

General Organizational Climate		
Correlation Coefficient	Structure	.541*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.011
N		21
Correlation Coefficient	Responsibility	.558*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.009
N		21
Correlation Coefficient	Reward	.762**
Sig. (bilateral)		0
N		21
Correlation Coefficient	Warmth	.579*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.006
N		21
Correlation Coefficient	Support	.847**
Sig. (bilateral)		0
N		21
Correlation Coefficient	Conflict	.671**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.001
N		21
Correlation Coefficient	Identity	.767**
Sig. (bilateral)		0
N		21

Table V shows the correlational analysis obtained between the organizational climate dimension and the general organizational climate. Likewise, it was deemed convenient to perform the same correlational analysis for the performance dimensions. To this respect, the dimensions that have a relation with the general job performance in the company PTS are quality with a significance of 0.011 ($p < 0.05$); interpersonal relationships with 0.003 ($p < 0.05$); initiative with 0.001

($p < 0.05$); teamwork with 0.022 ($p < 0.05$); organization with 0.001 ($p < 0.05$); and lastly, goal orientation with 0 ($p < 0.05$). In this case, all the performance dimensions have a relation with the general performance. Table VI shows the correlational analysis obtained between the job performance dimensions and the general job performance.

TABLE VI
 CORRELATION BETWEEN THE JOB PERFORMANCE DIMENSION AND THE GENERAL JOB PERFORMANCE

General job performance		
Correlation Coefficient	Quality	.701**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.001
N		20
Correlation Coefficient	Interpersonal Relations	.626**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.003
N		20
Correlation Coefficient	Initiative	.700**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.001
N		20
Correlation Coefficient	Team work	.509*
Sig. (bilateral)		0.022
N		20
Correlation Coefficient	Organization	.668**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.001
N		20
Correlation Coefficient	Results Orientation	.818**
Sig. (bilateral)		0.000
N		20

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The findings of this investigation demonstrate that, in the case of PTS Company Peru, there is a direct relation between organizational climate and job performance. This finding corresponds to the investigations which show the existence of a relation between the mentioned variables [39], [32], [33], [40]. Also, it is concluded that, in this case, there is consistency with the postulates presented by some authors, to the extent that they indicate that the climate is related and influences the action, behavior and performance of the collaborators [2], [41], [8], [9]. The result of this correlation also allows to state that, the better the perception of the climate, the greater the performance of the collaborators. Likewise, it allows to achieve the main objective and the validation of the main hypothesis.

The results of the investigation confirm the existence of a relation between the nine dimensions of the organizational climate and the general job performance. This result is interesting since it goes along with the findings of some studies [32], [33], where a relation was found in eight out of nine dimensions of the organizational climate with the job performance. Also, the results support that the dimensions that have been associated with the performance, in most studies, are support, risk, reward and structure [33]. Likewise, a relation between some specific dimensions of the organizational climate with the job performance could be found, eight out of nine dimensions of the organizational climate were related to some performance dimensions, except,

conflict, which was the only dimension which showed no relation at all. On the other hand, the most representative relations are the following: Responsibility dimension (climate) is understood as the standards, policies and procedures that must be carried out for the fulfillment of functions at work with the goal orientation dimension (performance). It is also important to consider the support dimension (climate), conceived as the feeling of collaboration perceived in the company, among the peers and the inferior and superior levels with the teamwork dimension (performance). Also, the standard dimension (climate) is conceived as the perception of the interest that the company has on the standard, procedure, policy and performance guidelines fulfillment with the organizational dimension (performance). Lastly, the reward dimension (climate) is understood as the perception about the existence of equity in the promotion and payment system with the quality dimension (performance).

VI. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The finding in this investigation enables to establish that, in the investigation area, to the extent that the organizational climate grows higher, the collaborators' performance will be better and thus better organizational results will be achieved.

Additionally, it can be emphasized that for the company, the organizational climate dimensions which have a higher relation with the collaborators' performance are warmth, organizational structure and support. The analysis of these findings enables the design of diverse action plans for the organization and the generation of better conditions in the company with which a better climate in the organization can be achieved and so a better performance of the collaborators, which translates in the achievement of the organizational objectives. However, the study was carried out in a specific sample and context which prevents to generalize the results and conclusions. Therefore, it is necessary to deepen the investigations dealing with organizational climate and job performance in all kinds of organizations, in order to achieve a better understanding of the different realities regarding the human management. Only so, it would be possible to generalize the results and prevent behaviors in other contexts about this important topic which helps us understand the action effectiveness in the different organizational climate dimensions and the job performance that facilitates the decision making among the human capital managers in the different kinds of organization.

TABLE VII
CORRELATIONS BETWEEN THE ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE AND THE JOB PERFORMANCE DIMENSIONS (CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS)

	Quality	Interpersonal relations	Initiative	Team work	Organization	Results Orientation
Correlation Coefficient	-0.256	-0.256	-0.276	-0.22	-0.099	,52*
Sig. (bilateral)	0.276	0.275	0.239	0.347	0.679	0.03
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	0.187	-0.039	-0.248	0.097	0.154	,624**
Sig. (bilateral)	0.429	0.869	0.292	0.686	0.517	0.029
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	,612**	0.304	,548*	0.072	-0.054	0.176
Sig. (bilateral)	0.025	0.192	0.0174	0.762	0.821	0.459
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	-0.129	0.07	-0.082	0.176	,583*	0.183
Sig. (bilateral)	0.587	0.771	0.73	0.459	0.031	0.44
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	0.051	,547*	0.137	,48	-0.159	0.155
Sig. (bilateral)	0.83	0.016	0.565	0.0423	0.502	0.513
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	,426	0.069	-0.139	,694**	-0.165	-0.004
Sig. (bilateral)	0.043	0.773	0.558	0.012	0.488	0.985
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	,61**	-0.05	-0.203	-0.249	,620**	-0.354
Sig. (bilateral)	0.016	0.833	0.39	0.289	0.004	0.125
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	0.004	-0.006	-0.134	-0.395	-0.136	-0.054
Sig. (bilateral)	0.986	0.979	0.572	0.085	0.566	0.822
N	20	20	20	20	20	20
Correlation Coefficient	0.065	-0.034	,512	-0.011	-0.086	,590*
Sig. (bilateral)	0.785	0.886	0.017	0.965	0.717	0.042
N	20	20	20	20	20	20

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